

Eco-friendly functional cellulose paper as a fire alarming via wireless warning transmission for indoor fireproofing

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Abstract

Herein, a strategy for fabricating wallpaper-based smart fire-warning systems to monitor and mitigate indoor fires is proposed. The fire-warning system, based on eco-friendly cellulose paper (CP), is produced via a simple dip-coating technique and provides flexibility, rapid low-temperature warning, and novel local and remote wireless signal conversion capability. Specifically, this fire-warning system can balance flexibility and flame retardancy, reducing the negative impact on the mechanical properties after adding flame retardants. Furthermore, the proposed fire-warning system meets the critical requirement of a fast low-temperature warning, showing warning messages within 2 s under 250 °C, decreasing the response temperature below the combustion temperature of common materials (> 300 °C). Moreover, the luminosity and temperature data collected can be sent to local and remote computers by wireless conversion. This work gives insight into the new generation of low-temperature smart fire-warning systems,

including the contribution of wireless warning signal transmission to achieve smart and efficient fire detection.

Keywords: smart wallpaper-based fire alarm; cellulose paper; low-temperature warning; wireless signal conversion;

1. Introduction

The increasingly frequent fires, especially under indoor ambient, represent a major social problem [1]. Therefore, an increased interest has been in developing novel and highly efficient fire control systems. In particular, smart early fire-warning systems have arisen as potential candidates in response to the high demand for fire-control strategies. Their rapid activation before violent fire propagation provides longer evacuation times [2, 3]. Moreover, early fire-warning systems exhibit excellent functionality due to their effortless implementation into daily household items, such as wires, wallpaper, smart fabrics, or decoration. Amongst, wallpaper-based fire-warning sensors are one operating and efficient approach for indoor fire detection. Specifically, using eco-friendly CP sourced from cotton, wood, or bamboo as the wallpaper endows sustainability, strong stability, and biocompatibility with the system [4-6]. Thus, wallpaper-based systems are emerging as new fire alert strategies, but there are yet some challenges that these systems need to face before becoming a well-established fire-warning technique.

Although conventional smoke and gas fire sensors present efficiency in fire management, they have certain drawbacks. Smoke detectors are strongly associated with color, location, shape, and optical density, which can arouse low sensitivity, low accuracy, and poor reliability [7]. Similarly, stability is a significant challenge for gas detectors [8]. For these reasons, thermo-sensitive fire-warning systems have taken the lead and are currently the most prevalent systems [2, 3]. Thermo-sensitive strategies require materials with temperature-responsiveness properties, like graphene

oxide (GO) - the current gold candidate due to its marvelous surface chemical performance.

The unique structure of GO endows it with excellent hydrophilicity, negatively charged nature, high electronic mobility, and temperature sensitivity [9-11]. The conductive behavior of GO is exceptionally responsive to temperature changes, shifting from an insulating state at room temperature to a conductive state at elevated temperatures. This advantage has been widely reported for GO-based fire-warning systems. For example, Qiu *et al.* fabricated a fire sensor using poly(oxyethylene)/GO/montmorillonite nanocomposite paper with a response time of 3 s at 300 °C [12]. Xu *et al.* showed that a GO-wrapped melamine formaldehyde sponge generated a warning within 33 s at 300 °C [13]. Cao *et al.* used a GO-based film as a fire warning showing a response within 3 s at 300 °C and 1 s at 350 °C [14]. All these GO-based thermo-sensitive fire alarms exhibited a rapid sign corresponding to different temperatures (response temperatures) within a short time. However, most warning temperatures are not lower than 300 °C and hover near violent combustion temperatures, resulting in a high possibility for fire propagation. Additionally, current systems rarely focus on the multifunction of these materials and other applications, such as wireless connectivity, strongly linked to comprehensive performance, smart modernization, and practical application.

Previous work from our group, including CP-based and GO film-based fire-warning systems, has shown a significant decrease in the response temperature up to 250 °C - lower than the minimum combustion temperature of substrate materials [15-17]. However, we find the addition of organic flame retardants plays a negative role in the mechanical properties of GO-based systems. Excellent flexibility is a critical feature of fire-warning systems, especially for the CP-based fire-warning sensor. So, how to balance flame retardancy and flexibility has yet to be realized.

This work focuses on achieving a balance by optimizing flame retardancy and flexible

performance. Introducing a flexible molecular segment is one approach to improving the flexibility of materials. For example, poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) has excellent structural flexibility, amphiphilicity, and biocompatibility [18-20]. In addition, PEO can be dissolved into water, which is advantageous to mix with GO aqueous solution. Moreover, PEO can form film, which is helpful for the formation of GO [18].

Compared with other fire management systems, one benefit of smart fire-warning systems is the transmission of detected fire information. Efficient and accurate signal conversion is essential to evaluate a fire-warning system. Commonly, fire-warning systems employ conventional warning signal types, *i.e.*, traditional lamps to generate light or buzzers to generate beep. However, environmental conditions or visual limitations can diminish the sensitivity of conventional conversion ways. In contrast, wireless signal transmission can solve these problems and be more in line with intelligent development. In our previous work, we proposed wireless signal conversion methods containing screen displays, remote multiple computer displays, and light intensity detection [15-17]. However, they do not involve temperature sensors yet. Therefore, developing temperature sensors has aroused considerable attention, which can improve the accuracy and expand the application of fire-warning systems.

Herein, a CP-based fire-warning system with a low-temperature warning, ultrafast response, flexibility, remote wireless luminosity signal transmission, and novel temperature-aid wireless signal conversion ability is studied.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

Trimethoxymethylsilane (MTM) solution, N, N-dimethylformamide solution (DMF, ACS reagent, 99.8%), and PEO powder were from Sigma-Aldrich Chemical Co. Commercial GO powder was

provided by Changzhou Sixth Element Materials Technology Co. Ltd (China). Modified carbon nanotube power (NH₄-CNT) was supplied by XFNANO Co., China. Deionized water was provided by the water purification system in the laboratory.

2.2 Preparation for P_xM_y@GO films and modified CP

The P_xM_y@GO films were fabricated by the simple layer-by-layer method. As shown in **Scheme 1a**, homogenous GO, MTM, PEO, and NH₄-CNT solutions were prepared for subsequent use. First, GO and MTM solutions were mixed and stirred for 0.5 h to improve the dispersion. Subsequently, the PEO solution was added to the above-mentioned solution, which was then magnetically stirred for 2 h for the final homogenous composition. Finally, P_xM_y@GO films were obtained by the blade coating method. Detailed information and related analysis about P_xM_y@GO films are displayed in **Table S1**, **Fig S1**, **Fig S2**, and **Fig. S3**, where x and y represent the concentration of PEO and MTM, respectively. In addition, CP was selected as substrate material, and the above-mentioned homogenous solution was applied to modify to obtain modified CP (GCP) via the dip-coating method (**Scheme 1b**). Next, the NH₄-CNT solution was sprayed onto the GCP surface to gain the final fire-warning sample (N@GCP).

Scheme 1. Schematic illustration of the fabrication procedures: (a). P_xM_y@GO film; (b). the modified CP.

2.3 Characterization

A Thermo Fisher Nicolet 5700 spectrometer with ATR mode was used to obtain the Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectrum. The Philip X' Pert PRO diffractometer was used to gain the X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns. Renishaw PLC Raman spectrometer was applied to get Raman spectra. A scanning electron microscopy (SEM) instrument of EVO MA15 from Germany was employed to obtain SEM micrograph images. TA Q50 instrument was used to get thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) curves under an air environment. TA instrument of Q800 was operated to perform dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). The program for the DMA test was from -120 °C to 25 °C at a heating rate of 2 °C/min. Q800 was also employed to carry out a tensile test. Microscale combustion calorimeter (MCC) was applied to achieve combustion behavior. A Keysight 3458A multimeter was performed for the electrical resistance measurements.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Optimization of mechanical property and flame retardancy

3.1.1 Structural characteristics of P_xM_y@GO films

Firstly, the structural features of functional GO-based films were studied. As observed in **Fig. 1a**, the FTIR spectrum of each sample displays characteristic peaks according to their composition. After the modification of MTM, the typical peak around 1020 cm⁻¹ assigned to Si-O-Si appears in MTM-modified films [21-23]. This might be due to the condensed reaction between hydrolyzed MTM themselves or between hydrolyzed MTM and the hydroxyl group of GO [24, 25], demonstrating the successful introduction of MTM into GO. Moreover, the XRD curves of each film in **Fig. 1b** display the expected maxima. Pure GO film has one sharp peak at $2\theta \approx 11.8^\circ$ to show the interlayer distance, corresponding to the (001) diffraction peak [26, 27]. However, the peaks of M₁₅@GO and M₂₀@GO shift to $2\theta \approx 10.7^\circ$, indicating the increased interlayer distance

compared to pure film. Pure PEO film has two typical peaks of $2\theta \approx 19.1^\circ$ and $2\theta \approx 23.2^\circ$, consistent with previous works [28, 29]. The $P_{15}@GO$ and $P_{20}@GO$ exhibit the characteristic PEO peaks at the same position as pure PEO film, but the further lower of (001) diffraction peak for GO. The downward shift of the peak demonstrates extended interlayer distance, which might be attributed to the common insertion of the PEO and MTM chains [30]. Moreover, Raman analysis is used to check the structural changes of defects and edge groups in carbon materials [31]. Results are represented by the I_D/I_G value (**Fig. 1c**). Compared with pure GO film, the I_D/I_G ratios of single MTM or PEO-modified films slightly increase. The ratios of the $P_xM_y@GO$ exhibit a further rise. These results might be related to the more structural defects of films after modification. Both of these results give insight into the chemical state of the modified film.

Fig. 1. Structural characteristics of functional GO-based films: (a) FTIR spectrum; (b) XRD diffraction patterns; (c) I_D/I_G value based on Raman spectra.

3.1.2 Combustion behaviors of P_xM_y@GO films

The fire resistance performance is evaluated for all the P_xM_y@GO films by their combustion behaviors. The weight change over time was recorded by TGA curves shown in **Fig. 2a**. The weight of each film goes down with a temperature up to 700 °C. Both P₁₅@GO and P₂₀@GO films burned out completely, demonstrating no significant difference by PEO concentration. However, the residual weight of M₁₅@GO and M₂₀@GO films display a noticeable increase at high temperatures. Additionally, for the GO-based films with co-modification of PEO and MTM, the carbon residual char content is in the following sequence: P₂₀M₁₅@GO < P₁₅M₁₅@GO < P₁₅M₂₀@GO < P₂₀M₂₀@GO. These results demonstrate that the introduction of MTM improves the fire resistance of GO-based films under high temperatures.

The films were observed under an alcohol lamp to analyze the real-time morphology changes of the paper for the exploration of combustion behavior intuitively. As depicted in **Fig. 2b**, neat GO film is burned out entirely under an alcohol lamp after burning for 40 s. P₁₅@GO and P₂₀@GO films are burned out within 30 s, consistent with the above TGA result. When the co-assistance of PEO and MTM are applied to GO film, their combustion behavior shows noticeable improvement. Even if the modified films are burned for 90 s, they can maintain the original shape to a certain extent. Comparing the shape change, P₂₀M₂₀@GO, and P₁₅M₁₅@GO film exhibits the best fire resistance performance, showing better fire durability under a flame, which can provide the basis for a fire-warning system.

Fig. 2. (a) TGA curves of functional GO-based films; (b) photographs images of burning functional GO-based films under an ignitor at different times.

3.1.3 Mechanical performance of P_xM_y@GO films

The balance between mechanical performance and flame retardancy is beneficial to improve comprehensiveness. Apart from flame retardancy, the mechanical properties of the films were studied via DMA. Here, the DMA analysis containing storage modulus, loss modulus, and $\tan \delta$ for all the P_xM_y@GO films under the test condition of a frequency of 1 Hz and a dynamic strain of 0.03% are given in **Fig. 3**. In **Fig. 3a**, the storage modulus (E') for P₁₅@GO, P₁₅M₁₅@GO, and P₁₅M₂₀@GO films increase sequentially with the increased content of MTM. Identically, the E' value for the P₂₀ series with a slightly higher concentration of PEO displays the same trend. Moreover, the E' value increases with more MTM content, which could be associated with the

"stiff" or "flimsy" situation of the films [32], the compatibility between MTM and GO, [33] or MTM acting as reinforcing fillers [34]. In addition, the E'' value for all films shown in **Fig. 3b** presents a similar comparative tendency as the change of the E' value. However, the E'' value gradually increases as the temperature increases. This implies the enhanced fluidity for molecular chain and improved compatibility, which also demonstrates a response to dissipate the applied energy [32]. Compared to the curves in **Fig. 3c**, a maximum peak in $\tan \delta$ is slightly visible for MTM-modified films, which is closely related to the chain motion, viscoelasticity, and the glass transition temperature [35]. This means that MTM negatively influences the mobility of PEO segments, which implies the importance of the balance between MTM and PEO content.

Fig. 3. Mechanical property of functional GO-based films vis temperatures from - 120 °C to 25 °C: (a) storage modulus (E'); (b) loss modulus (E''); (c) damping factor ($\tan \delta$). (d) the tensile strength curves of functional GO-based films.

In all the stretch curves (**Fig. 3d**), each film exhibits different tensile strength and elongation at break. For P₁₅@GO and P₂₀@GO films, the maximum stress reaches near 5 MPa while their elongation at break shows the best results, which is closely related to the slippage of PEO chains well dispersed into GO [34], or the strong interactions between oxygen functional groups of PEO and GO [36, 37]. After adding MTM, the maximum tensile strength gradually increases while diminishing the elongation at the break of films. Usually, silane coupling can reinforce the mechanical property that has been proved in previous works [38, 39]. At the same time, the addition of nanoparticles would inhibit the motion of the molecular chain, leading to decreased elongation at break to a certain extent [38]. Comparably, P₁₅M₁₅@GO film has better mechanical properties. Combined with the flame-retardant analysis mentioned above, the corresponding concentration of P₁₅M₁₅@GO is selected for the following experiments.

3.2 Application of optimized functional nano-coating on CP

A prototype of a CP-based fire-warning system is made to exemplify the application of the above-mentioned optimized functional pre-designed solution. Furthermore, NH₄-CNT is selected as a bridge to enhance the formation of a conductive pathway at low temperatures when the sample is exposed to a flame, as shown in **Scheme 2**.

Scheme 2. Scheme illustration for the structure of modified CP.

3.2.1 Structural characteristics of CP-based fire-warning system

FTIR, XRD, SEM, and EDS were performed to check the structural features of CP, GCP, and N@GCP. From the FTIR curves in **Fig. 4a**, each paper has its representative peaks with peaks at about 3320 cm^{-1} , 2894 cm^{-1} , 1630 cm^{-1} , and 1428 cm^{-1} , attributing to the stretching vibration of the hydroxyl group, -CH stretching vibration of hydrocarbon constituent, the vibration of absorbed water, and bending vibrations of $-\text{CH}_2$ of cellulose, respectively [40]. Compared to the pure CP sample, the new peaks at around 1280 cm^{-1} , 947 cm^{-1} , and 843 cm^{-1} appear in GCP and N@GCP samples, corresponding to the characteristic peaks of PEO [41-43]. This result verifies the coating of the functional layer. In addition, the peak at 1590 cm^{-1} corresponding to the -NH group only appears in N@GCP, showing the successful coating of functional CNT [44]. XRD test is also used further to study the structure change (**Fig. 4b**). CP has two characteristic peaks corresponding to the characteristic (110) and (200) reflection peaks for CP [45, 46]. Rather, GCP and N@GCP have another peak at about $2\theta \approx 8.0^\circ$, corresponding to the (002) diffraction peak of GO. This peak shifts to a slightly lower peak in comparison to the peak for pure GO, which reveals the expanded layer distance [30].

Moreover, SEM, a powerful tool, is applied for surface morphology analysis, and the results are displayed in **Fig. 4c**. The pure CP shows a porous structure on the surface. However, the modified CP reveals a continuous surface topography. After introducing functional CNT, the surface of N@GCP becomes rough, and some small particles are on the surface, showing successful coating. The EDS images in **Fig. 4d** exhibit the elements in each paper, proving the successful coating of functional CNT as well.

Fig. 4. (a) FTIR spectrums, (b) XRD curves, (c) SEM images, and (d) EDS element mappings of the cross-section for CP and CP-based fire-warning system.

The stress-strain curves of the different CP-based fire-warning systems are presented in **Fig.**

5a. The stress increases of each paper with the long strain. However, the surface modification for each paper is different, leading to the distinct strength and elongation at break between them. The stress strength of N@GCP can increase up to 15 MPa. This might be caused by the introduction of CNT, which can also reflect the good adhesion of GO-MTM composite on the cellulose surface [47]. Additionally, the coated CP is folded into an airplane shape to further illustrate its flexibility (**Fig. 5b**). There is no visible breakage signal, even at the folded edges. Both results show the flexibility of modified paper, which provides different possibilities for the potential shape designs of the wallpaper-based fire-warning system.

Fig. 5 (a) The tensile strength curves of CP and CP-based fire-warning system; (b) images of folded coated paper.

3.2.2 Flame retardancy of CP-based fire-warning system

Excellent fire resistance is essential for a fire-warning system. Therefore, the flame retardancy of coated paper is verified via the results of TGA, MCC, and combustion behavior, as presented in **Fig. 6**. All the TGA curves in **Fig. 6a** show a descending tendency, but different remaining weight at high temperatures, with the following sequence: N@GCP > GCP > CP, indicating the improved flame retardancy after modification. Additionally, an MCC test was performed to record combustion parameters, including the peak heat release rate (HRR) and oxygen content. The peak HRR value is closely related to oxygen consumption [48]. As shown in **Fig. 6b**, GCP has less oxygen consumption than pure CP, leading to a lower peak HRR value. When GCP is further

modified by NH₄-CNT, the peak HRR value of N@GCP becomes slightly lower again, which displays the further reinforcement of fire resistance. Furthermore, the combustion behavior of samples under ignition treatment is carried out to observe the morphological change intuitively. From the optical images in **Fig. 6c**, neat CP burns out into ashes within 10 s. However, GCP and N@GCP still maintain their shape for burning for 90 s, resulting in a higher flame resistance, which can provide a solid foundation for manufacturing a fire-warning system.

The schematic illustration of the flame-retardant mechanism is shown in **Fig. 6d**. Under flame exposure, a functional layer on the surface of CP can form a protective layer composed of the accumulating silicon dioxide, which is primarily attributed to the burned MTM. Importantly, this physical layer can be used as thermal insulation to protect the substrate and as a barrier against oxygen release and heat transfer [49, 50].

Fig. 6 (a) TGA curves, (b) peak HRR and oxygen consumption change, and (c) photographs of the combustion process of pure paper and CP-based fire-warning system. (d) scheme illustration of the flame-retardant working mechanism.

3.2.3 Fire warning process of CP-based fire-warning system

The change in the conductive state is the response to the temperature of GO-based fire-warning systems. Thereby, it is crucial to study the electrical conductivity of samples as a function of temperature. In this work, the electrical resistance change is recorded to reflect a difference in the electric conductive state. To verify the response ability of samples at low temperatures, the heating source is constituted by an oven at 250 °C, and the electric resistance of fire-warning samples is collected over time. As seen in **Fig. 7a**, the electric resistance of GCP and N@GCP

gradually decreases with the increasing heating time, showing the same downward trend. But the declining rate for each sample is different. In particular, N@GCP has a faster descent, indicating a lower electric resistance after heating for the same time than GCP.

Furthermore, an ignitor is applied to burn the sample because this flame type is similar to a real flame. Identically, the electrical resistance of GCP and N@GCP are monitored during the whole combustion process, as shown in **Fig. 7b**. The electric resistance of GCP and N@GCP display the same decreasing trend under continued burning treatment. However, N@GCP presents a faster descent rate than GCP. However, it is worth noting that a turning point appears in the curve of electric resistance. This might result from the unstable state of the paper during the burning process. By contrast, an ignitor can provide more powerful thermo-energy, leading to a slight shape change during burning. This is consistent with the above shape change results during the continued burning process.

It has been proposed that one way to calculate response time is based on "trigger electric resistance" [3]. This method uses an electrical resistance threshold, 90 % of the initial electric resistance for this study. Following this method, the response time of each sample is obtained, and results are shown in **Fig. 7c**. In contrast, N@GCP has a slightly shorter response time than GCP, even if the thermal source is different. Using an ignitor can provide more energy to achieve a faster reduction of GO to form an electrical pathway, leading to a shorter response time. The response time of N@GCP is lower than 2 s, demonstrating that the warning occurs within the first 2 s. This result strongly proves the highly-sensitive warning ability of the fire-warning system in this work.

To explain how this fire-warning system works, simple fire-simulation scenarios are prepared. The change of lamp state (ON/OFF) is employed to send a warning signal. Images in **Fig. 7d** perform the evolution of the lamp state during the whole fire-warning simulation. At the

beginning of the simulation, the lamp is off. After burning, the fire-warning sample evolves into a conductive state, turning on the lamp. As the burning time increases, the light becomes brighter due to more formation of RGO. Notably, the warning signal can continue for at least 120 s under burning conditions.

Fig. 7 The electrical resistance change of cp-based fire-warning system under (a) 250 °C and (b) burning situation. (c) response time of fire-warning systems after heating and burning situation. (d) fire-warning simulation process of GCP and $N_i@GCP$ fire-warning systems under fire attack.

3.3 Working mechanism of the fire-warning process

GO-based fire-warning systems primarily rely on the change of conductive states for GO to respond to abnormal temperatures during combustion. The successful change of conductive state means the formation of RGO, which can lead to the corresponding structural change. To verify the successful reduction of GO, XRD, Raman, and SEM tests are carried out. The related results are presented in **Fig. 8**.

For the XRD curves of heating treated paper (**Fig. 8a**), two sharp peaks appear at about 15.8° and 21.7° , assigned to the (110) diffraction peak of CP and (200) diffraction peak or characteristic peak for RGO. It isn't easy to distinguish the assignment of a peak of 21.7° due to the overlap of the peak from CP and RGO. Additionally, the burned paper presents two small shoulder peaks at around 15.8° and 22.0° , respectively. This might result from the increased thickness of the char layer covering the surface of the paper. However, the comparison reveals that the structural changes of burned paper are more significant than that of heated paper. This might be attributed to the different content of the char layer caused by distinct thermo-energy.

Moreover, structure change is further revealed by the I_D/I_G value from Raman spectroscopy (**Fig. 8b**). The I_D/I_G value of heated paper slightly increases, and the further advanced I_D/I_G ratio of burned paper is observed compared to heated paper. The ratio assesses the average size of the sp^2 cluster of materials [31]. This result implies more formation of smaller fragments and more edge carbon atoms after combustion treatment, leading to a decreased graphitization degree [51].

The surface topography offers further insights into GO's structural changes. The morphologies of the heated and burned paper are depicted in **Fig. 8c** and **Fig. 8d**. After thermal treatment, a carbon layer is formed on the surface of the modified paper, leading to a continuous structure compared with the porous structure for CP. In contrast, particles appear on the surface, which might be from the heating treatment of CNT. The same phenomenon also can be seen in the burned paper. The SiO_2 network can be evidently observed in the image with high magnification, which can positively improve flame retardancy [49]. This is consistent with the above results.

All the results mentioned above demonstrate the successful reduction of GO. The reduction process is schematically shown in **Fig. 8e**. it is significant to note that structural damage could happen to basal carbon planes after thermal treatment. The defects could form in the carbon layer,

leading to an influence on conductivity [52].

Fig. 8 (a) XRD diffract grams, (b) I_D/I_G value of GCP and N@GCP after heating treatment at 250 °C and burning treatment. SEM images of (c) heated GCP and heated N@GCP, and (d) burned GCP and N@GCP. (e) schematic illustration of the proposed working mechanism after a fire warning.

3.4 Remote wireless conversion of monitored warning signal

Temperature and luminosity are highly correlated with fire development. Thus, a new temperature sensor combined with a luminosity sensor was employed to monitor these changes under a fire attack. As illustrated in **Fig. 9**, temperature and luminosity values are visualized once the sample is ignited. As a comprehensive overview, changes in luminosity are sent to a WiFi (wireless fidelity) network using a WiFi module connected to a photoresistor sensor. Thus, any

device connected to this network can access the data, including computers or cell phones. In addition, the real-time temperature is measured with a thermocouple and transmitted remotely via LoRA (long range radio), which is also connected to the WiFi network.

Fig. 9. Experimental set-up of the temperature and luminosity communication remote system.

For this study, different devices contribute to communicating the data from the heat source to the final user. As shown in **SV1**, both sensors - a photoresistor and a thermocouple - are placed close to the fire-warning paper to provide a faster response. They are connected to a microcontroller, i.e., MKRWAN1300, to send the data they provided. The microcontroller's serial port is used to visualize the temperature and luminosity values locally utilizing a computer, while additional modules are added to the microcontroller for remote communication.

Specifically, an ESP8266 WiFi board is physically connected to the microcontroller for the luminosity data. The data is sent to the WiFi network by introducing the network SSID and password in the WiFi board through the microcontroller. Furthermore, an HTTP link is generated to enter the web to read luminosity values from any device with internet access. The local monitoring allows higher acquisition rates (> 1 Hz) compared to the ones detected remotely (1 Hz).

It is important to note that both communication systems (local and remote) run at the same time, as shown in **SV1**.

For the temperature data, an Arduino MKRTherm shield is coupled into a LoRA emitter MKRWAN 1300; a wireless method shown in our previous works [15, 16, 53], and detailed analysis is shown in **S1**. However, the MKRTherm module has never been used before for this LoRa application and with luminosity sensors. Temperature data is sent remotely to a RAK2245 Pi Hat concentrator, which operates as a gateway and receives all the packages emitted by the MKRWAN1300. The RAK is also connected to the WiFi network, and data could be visualized in The Things of Stack (TTS) platform. Ubidots IoT software is programmed to be associated with TTS to plot the temperature line versus time (**SV1** and **S2**). This protocol allows the emitter and receiver to be separated up to 20 - 30 km in interurban areas and 2 km in urban ones, depending on the electromagnetic pollution, increasing the transmission distance and drastically reducing the power consumption compared to other remote communication protocols. Based on the above working principle of this warning communication system, once the wallpaper situation changes caused by a flame, the luminosity and temperature are monitored and provide precise information to the operators about the potential danger.

The response and signal conversion properties are essential for estimating one fire-warning system. A summary of previously reported fire-warning systems and this work is provided in **Table 1**. In comparison, this work offers a lower response temperature (250 °C) and accurate real-time temperature detection, leading to a lower fire risk and an improvement of the feasibility of practical applications.

Table 1. Comparison analysis between partial fire-warning systems.

Systems	Methods	solvents	Response	Response	Signal	Multifunction	Ref.
			Time / s	temperature			
Graphene/SF/FA/Ca ²⁺	electro-blown spinning	FA/Ca ²⁺	2	-	Yes	Self-adhesive, humidity	[54]
GO/BP-MoS ₂	vacuum filtration	-	1	-	-	-	[55]
SF/CAHIs battery	-	-	5	-	Yes	Self-healing	[56]
PA/GO/MXene	Dip-coating	water	2	250 °C	Yes	-	[17]
MV or ME paper	Evaporation	water	1.8	-	-	hydrophobicity	[57]
SPI/MSF/GN/CA	-	-	2	-	-	Tensile strength	[58]
<i>N@GCP</i>	<i>Dip-coating /Spary</i>	<i>water</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>250 °C</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>flexibility</i>	<i>this work</i>

^a SF:silk fibroin; FA:formic acid; BP: black phosphorene; MoS₂: molybdenum disulfide; CAHIs:Ca²⁺ hydro-iontronics; PA:phatic acid; MXene:titanium carbide; MV:titanium carbide/polyvinyl pyrrolidone; ME:titanium carbide/polyethylene glycol; SPI:soy protein isolate; MSG:sisal cellulose microcrystals; GN:graphene nanosheets; CA:citric acid.

4 Conclusion

A functional coating layer over modified paper is used as a fire warning system. It presents excellent flexibility and flame retardancy, which maintains shape under continued burning treatment, leading to a solid function for a fire-warning system. When the temperature increases to 250 °C or burning treatment, the warning signal can be monitored within 2 s, indicating the high sensitivity at low temperatures. In addition, it is possible to transmit local and remote messages with the hazard information simultaneously with a luminosity sensor and temperature sensor. The real-time temperature and luminosity change can be recorded and transferred to a computer or phone monitor within 20 km. This work aims to provide new insight into the next generation of smart fireproofing materials.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Xiaolu Li: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Writing-original draft & editing. **José Sánchez del Río Saez:** Partial writing-original draft preparation. **Antonio Vázquez-López:** Partial writing-original draft. **Xiang Ao:** Some figures prepared. **Raquel Sánchez Díaz:** Writing-review & editing. **De-Yi Wang:** Writing-review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this work.

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Appendix A. Supplementary Data

Supporting information

References

- [1] Kim Y., Park, D., Rie, D., 2023. Evaluation of the flame-retardant performance and fire risk of cellulose building finishing material due to the particle size of expandable graphite. *Sustainability* 15 (6), 5426. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15065426>.
- [2] Lv L.Y., Cao, C.F., Qu, Y.X., Zhang, G.D., Zhao, L., Cao, K., Song, P., Tang, L.C., 2022. Smart fire-warning materials and sensors: Design principle, performances, and applications. *Mater. Sci. Eng. R Rep.* 150, 100690. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mser.2022.100690>.
- [3] Li X., Vázquez-López, A., Sánchez del Río Sáez, J., Wang, D.Y., 2022. Recent advances on early-stage fire-warning systems: Mechanism, performance, and perspective. *Nano-Micro Lett.* 14 (1), 197. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40820-022-00938-x>.
- [4] Costes L., Laoutid, F., Brohez, S., Dubois, P., 2017. Bio-based flame retardants: When nature meets fire protection. *Mater. Sci. Eng. R Rep.* 117, 1-25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mser.2017.04.001>.

- [5] Cao S., Rathi, P., Wu, X., Ghim, D., Jun, Y.S. Singamaneni, S., 2020. Cellulose nanomaterials in interfacial evaporators for desalination: A “natural” choice. *Adv. Mater.* 33 (28), 2000922. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202000922>.
- [6] Dai X., Guo, Z., 2022. The gorgeous transformation of paper: From cellulose paper to inorganic paper to 2d paper materials with multifunctional properties. *J. Mater. Chem. A* 10 (1), 122-156. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1ta08410k>.
- [7] Gaur A., Singh, A., Kumar, A., Kumar, A. Kapoor, K., 2020. Video flame and smoke based fire detection algorithms: A literature review. *Fire Technol.* 56 (5), 1943-1980. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10694-020-00986-y>.
- [8] Jackson M. A., Robins, I., 1994. Gas sensing for fire detection measurements of CO CO₂ H₂ O₂ and smoke density in european standard fire tests. *Fire Saf. J.* 22 (2), 181-205. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0379-7112\(94\)90072-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0379-7112(94)90072-8).
- [9] Shao J.J., Lv, W. Yang, Q.H., 2014. Self-assembly of graphene oxide at interfaces. *Adv. Mater.* 26 (32), 5586-5612. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201400267>.
- [10] Li D., Müller, M.B., Gilje, S., Kaner, R.B., Wallace, G.G., 2008. Processable aqueous dispersions of graphene nanosheets. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 3 (2), 101-105. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nnano.2007.451>.
- [11] Wei Z., Wang, D., Kim, S., Kim, S.Y., Hu, Y., Yakes, M.K., Laracuente, A.R., Dai, Z., Marder, S.R., Berger, C., King, W.P., 2010. Nanoscale tunable reduction of graphene oxide for graphene electronics. *Science* 328 (5984), 1373-1376. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1188119>.
- [12] Qiu W.W., Yu, Z.R., Zhou, L.Y., Lv, L.Y., Chen, H., Tang, L.C., 2022. Facile fabrication of graphene oxide nanoribbon-based nanocomposite papers with different oxidation degrees and morphologies for tunable fire-warning response. *Nanomaterials* 12 (12), 1963. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano12121963>.
- [13] Xu H., Li, Y., Huang, N.J., Yu, Z.R., Wang, P.H., Zhang, Z.H., Xia, Q.Q., Gong, L.X., Li, S.N., Zhao, L. Zhang, G.D., 2019. Temperature-triggered sensitive resistance transition of graphene oxide wide-ribbons wrapped sponge for fire ultrafast detecting and early warning. *J. Hazard. Mater.* 363, 286-294. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2018.09.082>.
- [14] Cao C.F., Yu, B., Chen, Z.Y., Qu, Y.X., Li, Y.T., Shi, Y.Q., Ma, Z.W., Sun, F.N., Pan, Q.H., Tang, L.C., Song, P., 2022. Fire intumescent, high-temperature resistant, mechanically flexible graphene oxide network for exceptional fire shielding and ultra-fast fire warning. *Nano-Micro Lett.* 14 (1), 92. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40820-022-00837-1>.

- [15] Li X., del Río Saez, J.S., Ao, X., Xu, B. Wang, D.Y., 2022. Tailored p/si-decorated graphene oxide-based fire sensor for sensitive detection at low-temperature via local and remote wireless transmission. *Constr. Build. Mater.* 349, 128600. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2022.128600>.
- [16] Li X., del Río Saez, J.S., Ao, X., Vázquez-López, A., Xu, X., Xu, B. Wang, D.Y., 2022. Smart low-temperature responsive fire alarm based on mxene/graphene oxide film with wireless transmission: Remote real-time luminosity detection. *Colloids Surf. A Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* 651, 129641. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2022.129641>.
- [17] Li X., del Río Saez, J.S., Ao, X., Yusuf, A. Wang, D.Y., 2022. Highly-sensitive fire alarm system based on cellulose paper with low-temperature response and wireless signal conversion. *Chem. Eng. J.* 431, 134108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.134108>.
- [18] D'souza A.A. Shegokar, R., 2016. Polyethylene glycol (peg): A versatile polymer for pharmaceutical applications. *Expert. Opin. Drug. Deliv.* 13 (9), 1257-1275. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17425247.2016.1182485>.
- [19] Chen J., Spear, S.K., Huddleston, J.G. Rogers, R.D., 2005. Polyethylene glycol and solutions of polyethylene glycol as green reaction media. *Green Chem.* 7 (2), 64-82. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b413546f>.
- [20] Polu A.R. Rhee, H.W., 2015. Nanocomposite solid polymer electrolytes based on poly(ethylene oxide)/POSS-PEG (n=13.3) hybrid nanoparticles for lithium ion batteries. *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* 31, 323-329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiec.2015.07.005>.
- [21] Kang C., Huang, J., He, W., Zhang, F., 2010. Periodic mesoporous silica-immobilized palladium(II) complex as an effective and reusable catalyst for water-medium carbon-carbon coupling reactions. *J. Organomet. Chem.* 695 (1), 120-127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jorganchem.2009.09.036>.
- [22] Yan W., Liu, D., Tan, D., Yuan, P., Chen, M., 2012. Ftir spectroscopy study of the structure changes of palygorskite under heating. *Spectrochim. Acta A Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.* 97, 1052-1057. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2012.07.085>.
- [23] Madejová J.J.V.S., 2003. Ftir techniques in clay mineral studies. *Vib. Spectrosc.* 31 (1), 1-10. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2031\(02\)00065-6](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0924-2031(02)00065-6).
- [24] Yang H., Li, F., Shan, C., Han, D., Zhang, Q., Niu, L. Ivaska, A., 2009. Covalent functionalization of chemically converted graphene sheets via silane and its reinforcement. *J. Mater. Chem. A* 19 (26), 4632. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b901421g>.

- [25] Huang N.J., Cao, C.F., Li, Y., Zhao, L., Zhang, G.D., Gao, J.F., Guan, L.Z., Jiang, J.X. Tang, L.C., 2019. Silane grafted graphene oxide papers for improved flame resistance and fast fire alarm response. *Compos. B. Eng.* 168, 413-420. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2019.03.053>.
- [26] Maharana H.S., Rai, P.K., Basu, A., 2016. Surface-mechanical and electrical properties of pulse electrodeposited cu-graphene oxide composite coating for electrical contacts. *J. Mater. Sci.* 52 (2), 1089-1105. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-016-0405-7>.
- [27] Marcano D. C., Kosynkin D. V., Berlin J. M., Sinitskii A., Sun, Z., Slesarev, A., Alemany L. B. Lu, W., Tour, J. M., 2010. Improved synthesis of graphene oxide. *ACS Nano* 4 (8), 4806-4814. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nn1006368>.
- [28] Corrigan D.O., Healy, A.M. Corrigan, O.I., 2002. The effect of spary drying solutions of peg and lactose peg on their physicochemical properties.Pdf. *Int. J. Pharm.* 235 (1), 193-205. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5173\(01\)00990-5](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-5173(01)00990-5).
- [29] Uyar T. Besenbacher, F., 2009. Electrospinning of cyclodextrin functionalized polyethylene oxide (PEO) nanofibers. *Eur. Polym. J.* 45 (4), 1032-1037. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2008.12.024>.
- [30] Dong L., Hu, C., Song, L., Huang, X., Chen, N. Qu, L., 2016. A large-area, flexible, and flame-retardant graphene paper. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 26 (9), 1470-1476. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201504470>.
- [31] Krishnamoorthy K., Veerapandian, M., Mohan, R. Kim, S.J., 2011. Investigation of raman and photoluminescence studies of reduced graphene oxide sheets. *Appl. Phys. A* 106 (3), 501-506. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-011-6720-6>.
- [32] Saba N., Jawaid, M., Alothman, O.Y. Paridah, M.T. , 2016. A review on dynamic mechanical properties of natural fibre reinforced polymer composites. *Constr. Build. Mater.* 106, 149-159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2015.12.075>.
- [33] Parhizkar N., Ramezanzadeh, B. Shahrabi, T., 2018. Corrosion protection and adhesion properties of the epoxy coating applied on the steel substrate pre-treated by a sol-gel based silane coating filled with amino and isocyanate silane functionalized graphene oxide nanosheets. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 439, 45-59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2017.12.240>.
- [34] Chang Y.W., Lee, K.S., Lee, Y.W., Bang, J.H., 2015. Poly(ethylene oxide)/graphene oxide nanocomposites: Structure, properties and shape memory behavior. *Polym. Bull.* 72 (8), 1937-1948. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00289-015-1381-9>.

- [35] Baatti A., Erchiqui, F., Godard, F., Bussieres, D., Bebin, P., 2019. Dma analysis, thermal study and morphology of polymethylsilsesquioxane nanoparticles-reinforced hdpe nanocomposite. *J. Therm. Anal. Calorim.* 139 (2), 789-797. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-019-08497-x>.
- [36] Koduru H.K., Bruno, L., Marinov, Y.G., Hadjichristov, G.B., Scaramuzza N., 2019. Mechanical and sodium ion conductivity properties of graphene oxide–incorporated nanocomposite polymer electrolyte membranes. *J. Solid State Electrochem* 23 (9), 2707-2722. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10008-019-04359-6>.
- [37] Liu L., Gao, Y., Liu, Q., Kuang, J., Zhou, D., Ju, S., Han, B., Zhang, Z., 2013. High mechanical performance of layered graphene oxide/poly(vinyl alcohol) nanocomposite films. *Small* 9 (14), 2466-2472. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.201300819>.
- [38] Wang J., Ji, C., Yan, Y., Zhao, D., Shi, L., 2015. Mechanical and ceramifiable properties of silicone rubber filled with different inorganic fillers. *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 121, 149-156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2015.09.003>.
- [39] Park E.S., 2007. Mechanical properties and processibility of glass-fiber-, wollastonite-, and fluoro-rubber-reinforced silicone rubber composites. *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 105 (2), 460-468. <https://doi.org/10.1002/app.26063>.
- [40] Hospodarova V., Singovszka, E. Stevulova, N., 2018. Characterization of cellulosic fibers by ftir spectroscopy for their further implementation to building materials. *Am. J. Anal. Chem.* 09 (06), 303-310. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ajac.2018.96023>.
- [41] Chieng B.W., Ibrahim, N.A., Wan Yunus, W.M.Z., Hussein, M.Z., 2013. Poly(lactic acid)/poly(ethylene glycol) polymer nanocomposites: Effects of graphene nanoplatelets. *Polymers* 6 (1), 93-104. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym6010093>.
- [42] Shamel K., Ahmad, M.B., Jazayeri, S.D., Sedaghat, S., Shabanzadeh, P., Jahangirian, H., Mahdavi, M. Abdollahi, Y., 2012. Synthesis and characterization of polyethylene glycol mediated silver nanoparticles by the green method. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 13 (6), 6639-6650. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms13066639>.
- [43] Kolhe P. Kannan, R.M., 2003. Improvement in ductility of chitosan through blending and copolymerization with peg ftir investigation of molecular interactions. *Biomacromolecules* 4 (1), 173-180. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1021/bm025689+>.
- [44] Pawlak A., Mucha, M., 2003. Thermogravimetric and ftir studies of chitosan blends. *Thermochim. Acta* 396, 153-166. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-6031\(02\)00523-3](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-6031(02)00523-3).

- [45] Hwang Y., Park, H.J., Potthast, A. Jeong, M.J., 2020. Evaluation of cellulose paper degradation irradiated by an electron beam for conservation treatment. *Cellulose* 28 (2), 1071-1083. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-020-03604-w>.
- [46] Garvey C.J., Parker, I.H., Simon, G.P., 2005. On the interpretation of x-ray diffraction powder patterns in terms of the nanostructure of cellulose I fibres. *Macromol. Chem. Phys* 206 (15), 1568-1575. <https://doi.org/10.1002/macp.200500008>.
- [47] Jiang B., Zhang, T., Zhao, L. Huang, Y., 2017. Interfacially reinforced carbon fiber composites by grafting modified methylsilicone resin. *Compos Sci. Technol.* 140, 39-45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2016.12.022>.
- [48] Chen X., Yusuf, A., del Rio, J.S., Wang, D.Y., 2021. A facile and robust route to polyvinyl alcohol-based triboelectric nanogenerator containing flame-retardant polyelectrolyte with improved output performance and fire safety. *Nano Energy* 81, 105656. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2020.105656>.
- [49] Carosio F., Laufer, G., Alongi, J., Camino, G., Grunlan, J.C., 2011. Layer-by-layer assembly of silica-based flame retardant thin film on pet fabric. *Polym. Degrad. Stab.* 96 (5), 745-750. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2011.02.019>.
- [50] Kashiwagi T., Gilman, J.W., Butler, K.M., Harris, R.H., Shields, J.R., Asano, A., 1994. Flame retardant mechanism of silica gel silica. *Fire Saf. J.* 24, 277-289. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/1099-1018\(200011/12\)24:6<277::AID-FAM746>3.0.CO;2-A](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/1099-1018(200011/12)24:6<277::AID-FAM746>3.0.CO;2-A).
- [51] Yao P., Chen, P., Jiang, L., Zhao, H., Zhu, H., Zhou, D., Hu, W., Han, B.H. Liu, M., 2010. Electric current induced reduction of graphene oxide and its application as gap electrodes in organic photoswitching devices. *Adv. Mater.* 22 (44), 5008-5012. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201002312>.
- [52] Song L., Khoerunnisa, F., Gao, W., Dou, W., Hayashi, T., Kaneko, K., Endo, M. Ajayan, P.M., 2013. Effect of high-temperature thermal treatment on the structure and adsorption properties of reduced graphene oxide. *Carbon* 52, 608-612. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2012.09.060>.
- [53] Yusuf A., del Río, J.S., Ao, X., Olaizola, I.A., Wang, D.Y., 2022. Potential energy-assisted coupling of phase change materials with triboelectric nanogenerator enabling a thermally triggered, smart, and self-powered iot thermal and fire hazard sensor: Design, fabrication, and applications. *Nano Energy* 103, 107790. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2022.107790>.

- [54] Cao L., Liu, Q., Ren, J., Chen, W., Pei, Y., Kaplan, D.L. Ling, S., 2021. Electro-blown spun silk/graphene nanoionotronic skin for multifunctional fire protection and alarm. *Adv. Mater.* 33 (38), 2102500. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202102500>.
- [55] Qu Z., Xu, C.A., Li, X., Wu, Y., Wang, K., Zheng, X., Cui, X., Wu, X., Shi, J. Wu, K., 2021. Facile preparation of bp-mos₂/go composite films with excellent flame retardancy and ultrasensitive response for smart fire alarm. *Chem. Eng. J.* 426, 130717. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.130717>.
- [56] Liu Q., Li, X., Zhang, H., Ren, J., Yang, S., Cao, L., Liang, J., Ling, S., 2022. Intellisense silk fibroin ionotronic batteries for wildfire detection and alarm. *Nano Energy* 101, 107630. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2022.107630>.
- [57] Mao M., Yu, K.X., Cao, C.F., Gong, L.X., Zhang, G.D., Zhao, L., Song, P., Gao, J.F. Tang, L.C., 2022. Facile and green fabrication of flame-retardant ti₃c₂tx mxene networks for ultrafast, reusable and weather-resistant fire warning. *Chem. Eng. J.* 427, 131615. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.131615>.
- [58] Zhang Z., Yang, D., Yang, H., Li, Y., Lu, S., Cai, R., Tan, W., 2021. A hydrophobic sisal cellulose microcrystal film for fire alarm sensors. *Nano Lett.* 21 (5), 2104-2110. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.0c04789>.